

The Role of Education and Cognitive Growth in Shaping Characters

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***Abstract.** The article is about the dynamic personal development of Jack London's protagonist Martin Eden which is compared to Bloom's Taxonomy: remembering, understanding, applying and so on. Moreover, it also discusses the novel of "Mirage" by A. Qahhor. The events experienced in A. Qahhor's life served as the basis for his novel "Mirage". The author's humanistic and taciturn qualities are reflected in the character of Saidiy in "Mirage".*

***Keywords:** science, personal development, Bloom's Taxonomy, realist.*

INTRODUCTION.

Martin Eden and Ruth have different attitudes toward education. Martin believes it is not necessary to study trigonometry and algebra. Instead, he studies the teachings of Darwin and Spencer. Ruth, on the other hand, believes it is essential to study Latin, history, and the exact sciences. She emphasizes that knowing Latin would serve as a foundation for obtaining a profession in the future.

Ruth had completed her undergraduate studies at university. However, despite her higher education, she was unable to grasp the content of Martin's complex literary works. As described: "She was not original, not creative, and all her manifestations of culture on her part were harpings, but harpings of the others."

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

Martin's knowledge, meanwhile, surpassed even Ruth's: "In spite of every advantage of university training and equipment, it gave him mastery of the affairs of the world and life that she could never hope to possess."

The dynamic personal development of Jack London's character Martin Eden can be compared to Bloom's Taxonomy:

1. Remembering – Martin's effort to memorize grammatical rules, various phrases, and grammatical structures;
2. Understanding – his ability to comprehend the books he read;
3. Applying – the protagonist's engagement in discussions with others based on Spencer's philosophy;
4. Analyzing – Martin's developing ability to read and analyze articles in scientific journals in order to choose a distinctive realist direction in his creative writing;
5. Evaluating – Martin's ability to critically assess Nietzschean philosophy;
6. Creating – the protagonist's writing of literary works.

However, Ruth's character does not display any clear aspiration to pursue a specific profession in the future. Her friend Olney considers marriage to be "the girl's future." No intellectual (cognitive) development is observed in Ruth.

A. Qahhor's novel "*Mirage*" was published six times (1937, 1957, 1967, 1987, 1995, 2017), three of which were during the author's lifetime. The novel depicts the socio-political and historical atmosphere of the 1920s and 1930s.

The main character of the novel "*Mirage*" enters Saidiys Institute to study. During his student years, he makes many friends, such as Ehson and Shafrin. The author expresses his own emotions and experiences through the character of Saidiy. Character traits typical of the author are embodied in Saidiy. The author reimagines people he has met and known in real life within the novel. For example, Saidiy's close friend Ehson reminds one of Muhammadjon Qulmatov, a close friend of the author during his school years.

CONCLUSION.

The events experienced in A. Qahhor's life served as the basis for his novel "*Mirage*". Muhammadjon Qulmatov remained the author's close friend until the end of his life. Muhammadjon Qulmatov entered the Medical Institute in Moscow and attained the degree of Doctor of Medical Sciences.

The author's humanistic and taciturn qualities are reflected in the character of Saidiy in "*Mirage*". During his student years, Saidiy falls in love with a girl named Munisxon. Saidiy's calm, serious, and composed nature attracts Munisxon's attention. The character of Munisxon is portrayed in the novel as a feminine figure who, in the author's eyes, captivates Saidiy's heart with "her gentle voice and beauty." When Saidiy enrolled at the university, he would meet Munisxon every day; they would prepare lessons together and discuss unclear sentences from their books.

Saidiy would admire Munisxon's long, dark eyelashes and continue his lively conversations with her. The moments he spent studying with the girl he loved were the sweetest of his life. However, Munisxon rejects Saidiy's pure love and prefers wealth. She becomes fond of Muxtorxon, a character with the "weak-willed" traits recommended by her brother. The girl overlooks all of Muxtorxon's flaws and begins to search for good qualities in him. Saidiy, in turn, marries Soraxon, the daughter of a man named Murodxo'ja domla. This causes Saidiy and Munisxon to grow apart.

REFERENCES:

1. London J. Martin Eden. Ebook. – P.275.
2. Qahhor A. Sarob. – Toshkent: Zukko kitobxon, 2021. – B.295.
3. Kakharova M.Y. Bildungroman Elements and Human Endurance in the Prose of Jack London and Abdulla Qahhor // International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research and Development. – Volume 10, issue 12, India –2023, e-ISSN 2394-6334. (Impact factor SJIF-8.854).